

From Oral History to Metadata? Report from the Oral History of Radio Archivists (OHRA) Pilot Project

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About Impresso

The ‘Impresso – Media Monitoring of the Past II: Beyond Borders’ project (2023-2027)¹ aims to pioneer new approaches for exploration of Western European newspaper and radio sources in five languages and to advance innovative practices in historical research with transnational and transmedia perspectives. As such, it promises to allow the joint exploration of historical media content across time, languages, and national borders. Building on the first Impresso project (2017-2020) that created a research infrastructure for Swiss and Luxembourgish newspaper sources, the current project represents an expansion in geographical and linguistic scope, as well as media type. Accordingly, it promises to not only generate innovative interfaces for the exploration and computational processing of enriched historical print collections, but also those of radio, which span, for example, audio recordings, transcribed speech, typescripts and accompanying archival metadata.

Challenges of newspaper and radio sources

The addition of radio collections as part of the second Impresso project introduces a new level of complexity. While many historical newspaper collections may also have gaps, in most European contexts they generally tend to be well-preserved by national libraries and archives, and included in mass digitization projects since the 2000s (Ehrmann, Bunout, and Clavert 2022, 1–5). By contrast, the emergence of European broadcast collections in the 1930s were generally characterised by the creation of radio programme recordings for internal needs, predominantly for the purposes of re-use in programming (Birdsall and Harrison 2022). Early radio collections in Europe often comprise pre-recordings or partial recordings, rather than the systematic recording and documentation of broadcast transmissions, a practice that was only introduced at some national broadcasters with the transition to digital archiving methods from around 2000 onwards. In addition, institutional radio collections may include recordings over multiple formats (e.g. wire, disc, analog/digital tape), recordings donated by amateur collectors, and gaps/inconsistencies in descriptive and technical metadata.

Neither newspapers nor radio sources allow for complete and representative reconstruction of past media landscapes and present distinct challenges for historians: Newspapers are overwhelming through their sheer abundance of preserved materials. In contrast, radio research faces the scarcity of preserved recordings and the variety of different sources.

¹ <https://impresso-project.ch/>

The OHRA project

Overall, Impresso is committed to the idea of providing transparency regarding the composition of the historical media corpus, the process of semantic enrichment and its implications and the representation of enriched media sources in its interfaces. In this context, the “Oral History of Radio Archivists” (OHRA) project strives to help users understand the intricacies of radio collections, inform their reasoning and point them to relevant resources beyond the Impresso platform. Impresso II’s future users will be able to search and compare radio and newspaper sources, but may be less familiar with the institutional, technical and/or archival conditions influencing the available corpus of digitized recordings and enriched metadata. For this reason, and in line with the principle of transparency, OHRA has the intention of exploring possibilities to collect and represent in a comparable manner contextual information between available collections within the Impresso II research infrastructure: What information about radio archives is relevant for researchers and missing from the existing metadata? Which of this information could be added by an archivist? As such, we recognise that there is often crucial knowledge preserved in current radio archivists’ memories that cannot be inferred from institutional records. In line with recent archivist knowledge transfer initiatives (van Dalen and Šičarov 2021), we identify oral history interviews as a productive method for eliciting key insights about radio collections, the conditions of their creation, stewardship and (digital) preservation.

We identified three main information needs for which an oral history approach appears promising: First, researchers need to understand the composition and content of a given archival collection. This includes evolving archival policies, source prioritisation during digitisation, variabilities in audio/data quality over time and unexpected data in the collection. Second, researchers need to identify additional, relevant resources. These resources may, for example, be created by other institutions or amateur historians, previous research projects. Third, researchers need to gain insights into forthcoming projects (e.g. collection digitisation) or other relevant information not yet announced publicly. OHRA’s goal is to collect such information and to make it available to Impresso users to allow critical usage of the data we provide and to help guide their further research.

Related work: Oral history in Media History and Metadata quality assessment

Oral history, as a methodology for data collection and analysis, has long been a key approach within humanities research. More recently, there has been an increased interest in using oral history research data within digital humanities research, and the growth of a field of digital oral history (Boyd and Larson 2014; Flinn et al. 2024; Dalen and Šičarov 2021). The value of oral history for histories of broadcasting has gained more traction in recent years, yet it is only more recently that projects like ‘Connective Histories of the BBC’ have explored the possibilities for embedding oral histories of media institutions within web interfaces that allow for full-text searches of interview data (Sichani and Hendy 2021). Previous research infrastructures that allowed exploration of print, radio and television archival collections, such as CLARIAH Media Suite, made a concerted effort to provide information on the datasets (“Sound and Vision Radio Archive (up to 2018, iMMix Version, Deprecated) - CLARIAH Labs Dataset Registry” 2018; “Radio Collection DAAN’, CLARIAH Media Suite” 2024). However, there has not been a rigorous attempt to extract, compare and contextualise the metadata that accompany historical radio collections, either through oral history interviews or exploring possible means of visually representing such information.

Completeness	The element, property, and/or attribute is present.
Accuracy	Information is correct both semantically and syntactically.
Accessibility	Metadata can be read by both humans and machines.
Conformance to expectations	Values adhere to the expectations of your defined user communities (both internal and external).
Consistency	Semantic and structural values and elements are represented in a consistent manner across records. Values are consistent within your domain.
Timeliness	When the resource changes, the metadata is updated accordingly. When additional metadata becomes available or when metadata standards change, the metadata associated with the resource changes.
Provenance	You have information about the source of the metadata, and you can track metadata transformations back to the original form of the metadata record.

Table 1: Non-exhaustive overview of metadata quality criteria developed by the DLF Metadata Assessment Working Group.

Metadata quality assessment is a well recognised challenge for data providers in the cultural heritage sector and beyond. As an example, Table 1 offers a non-exhaustive overview of common metadata quality criteria developed by the DLF Metadata Assessment Working Group (Gavrilis et al. 2015). These criteria reflect common problems and information needs for researchers. Inspired by these categories, OHRA strives to collect expert knowledge for metadata quality assessment albeit choosing a qualitative approach which seeks to complement existing metadata rather than analysing it.

Oral History Interview Setup and Analysis

We selected interview partners based on two principles: They represent one of Impresso’s project partners and have a seniority level which corresponds to deep knowledge about the histories of the collections they provide. OHRA interviews take place in two rounds: A first (partially completed at the time of writing) focuses on the institutional history of radio archives. This includes reflections on the implications of institutional mergers, changing missions and archival strategies as well as the adoption of digitisation techniques. A second round will focus specifically on the intricacies of the collections the archive provides to the Impresso project and will be conducted in partnership with Impresso’s EPFL-based team, responsible for the ingestion and modeling of historical media collections. All interviews are semi-structured and based on a list of questions made available to the interview partner beforehand (see Table 2). Interviews are recorded using Cisco Webex and rely on their automated transcription service together with manual note keeping. Despite the inherent imperfections in automated transcription, Anthropic’s Claude AI turned out to be helpful to retrieve relevant interview quotes based on these notes, however always subject to manual validation.

History of the collection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How did preservation activities start in your archive? What were the priorities? What was there before systematic archival-work and documentation? 2. Are there any unexpected “gems” in your collections? E.g. artefacts/objects/recordings/catalogues/lists/index cards - any form of document, documentation or object one would not at first expect to find in there? 3. What is the best way to explore your collections beyond what will be in Impresso? 4. Can you think of a research project which used your data which was particularly successful in your view? 5. Are you aware of other institutions which contain documents related to your collections? For example, radio magazines, programming indices provided by amateur groups?
Digitisation history	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How did digitisation start? How have titles been selected for digitisation? 2. Is there an even distribution of OCR and/or speech to text quality in your collections? Is there a way to know what will likely be hidden due to poor quality?
Data shared with Impresso (tbd if applicable at the time of interview)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. On which grounds were you able to share the data with us? 2. To which extent is it (not) representative of your collection? 3. In the Impresso team we have historians working on colonialism, feminism, history of format evolution in newspapers and radios and other topics. Imagine a historian sees your data in Impresso and wants to work with it. What should this person be aware of? 4. Which advice would you give for non-expert historians who want to work with radio data?

Table 2: *Questions for the semi-structured interviews provided to interview partners beforehand.*

First results

The OHRA project is still in its early and formative stages but, nevertheless, has already yielded promising insights into two radio collections: DeutschlandRadio via an interview with Jörg Wehling, head of documentation and archival services and Bas Agterberg, curator at the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision (NISV). The interviews revealed hitherto unknown aspects about both institutions’ collections, for example the existence of interview collections dating back to the 1930s in the case or the challenges to integrate data from different institutions in the case of the NISV.

Both interviews have shown that they can support the main user needs we identified above. To illustrate this, we have developed first drafts of researcher-facing information based on the interview with Bas Agterberg on the history of NISV’s collections. Figure 1 presents a timeline which reflects the periodization introduced by Agterberg and includes collection-specific information such as references to the Netherland’s colonial broadcasts and private recordings of Radio Oranje during World War II.

During the interviews we also discussed the intricacies inherent in any cultural heritage collection. Table 3 gives an overview of caveats to consider when working with NISV's collections together with general advice on how to approach the collections. Future work will focus on separating generally applicable caveats (early radio recordings being rare and fragmentary) from collection-specific ones (e.g. searches in Media Suite and DAAN will produce different results). Complementary to this, Table 4 gives an overview of collection-specific opportunities identified by our interview partner. This includes an overview of forthcoming data which will become available in the near future, another important source of information for researchers. References to existing resources generated by the institutions (e.g. the NISV Wiki²) and the public (e.g. Wikipedia) will be integrated as well wherever they provide meaningful additional information.

Figure 1: First draft of a timeline of NISV's collections targeting researcher needs.

² <https://wiki.beeldengeluid.nl/index.php/Hoofdpagina>.

Early Radio Recordings (1920s-1940s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recordings are rare and often fragmentary • Many recordings were accidental or made for specific purposes rather than preservation • Often only contains partial content rather than full programs
World War II Period (1940-1945)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radio Oranje (London) collection includes recordings provided by individual citizens as well as created by the broadcaster • Selection bias based on what was chosen for recording
Historical Preservation Bias (1950s-1980s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on journalistic reuse value rather than historical preservation • Materials often taped over or discarded
Conservation Tapes Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple unrelated recordings on single tapes • Complicated to work with specific collections • Poor documentation practices • Duplicates exist
Database and Search Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different search results between systems (Media Suite vs. DAAN), advice to use both in parallel • Date search issues may yield false positive results • Beware of incomplete metadata transfer between systems
Data integration after Institutional Merger	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital database doesn't maintain collection relationships • Difficult to identify sub-collections or related materials
Documentation and Context Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Much institutional knowledge was kept in archivists' heads rather than documented • Handwritten notes not systematically archived • Complicated provenance trails
Access Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some collections require direct archive contact • Different systems have different levels of accessibility • Language barriers with audio content
General advice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Always check multiple systems (DAAN, Media Suite, and direct archive contact) • Consider the broader historical context of preservation • Be aware that absence of material doesn't mean events didn't happen • Contact the archive directly for comprehensive research

Table 3: Overview of caveats to consider when working with NISV collections.

Complementary Sources for Missing Broadcasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program guides • Broadcast logs with detailed information • Photographs (especially for television)
Recent Digital Collections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete 24/7 broadcasts since 2012
Biannual Complete Recording Weeks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two weeks per year of all Dutch channels including commercial ones
International Comparative Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International News Exchange materials • Opportunities to study how different countries use same footage • Extensive collection awaiting full integration
Phillips PHOHI Collection (1930s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Colonial radio broadcasts to Indonesia • Unique preservation due to time difference needs
Academic Audio Collection (from 1930s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early academic use of audio recordings • Interview collections
Podcasts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Full podcast archives recently acquired

Table 4: Overview of opportunities for researchers working with NISV collections.

Conclusion

This abstract gave an introduction to the OHRA project. Whilst still in an early stage, we can report that interviews with long-serving radio archivists have proven to be a viable means to obtain research-relevant information which is not readily available via public sources or can be extracted from metadata provided by the respective institution. Using the Netherlands Institute for Sound & Vision as an example, we have showcased how information extracted from interviews can help to address the user needs identified beforehand. This includes information about research opportunities, caveats, forthcoming data as well as a timeline of the collection history tailored to the needs of researchers.

These first interviews also pointed to the heterogeneity and complexity of radio archive collections. The organisation of radio archival sources is inherently linked to individual archivists, their visions, strategies and practical operational decision-making. Researchers and archivists need to become aware of this in order to make sense of the collections. This last point highlights the urgency to invest in a systematic approach to preserve the rich but also ephemeral institutional knowledge of archivists that is often lost as a consequence of retirement or career change.

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